

ISSN 2181-9130

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9130

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 5

ТОШКЕНТ-2023

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

№5 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9130-2023-5>

Бош муҳаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Abdurasulova Qumriniso Raimqulovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Fayziev Shoxrud Farmonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ | EDITORIAL BOARD

12.00.01 - ДАВЛАТ ВА ҲУҚУҚ НАЗАРИЯСИ ВА ТАРИХИ. ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАЪЛИМОТЛАР ТАРИХИ / ТЕОРИЯ ПРАВА И ГОСУДАРСТВА, ИСТОРИЯ ПРАВОВЫХ УЧЕНИЙ / THEORY OF LAW AND STATE, HISTORY OF LEGAL DOCTRINES

Boboyev Halimboy Boboyevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Ahmedshaeva Mavlyuda Axatovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Muxitdinova Firyuza Abdurashidovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Adilxodjayeva Surayyo Maxkamovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Sattorov Abdug'affor

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Artur Gambaryan

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Armaniston)

Yosuke Shamoto

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Yaponiya)

12.00.02 - КОНСТИТУЦИОННИЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МАЪМУРИЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МОЛИЯ ВА БОЖХОНА ҲУҚУҚИ / КОНСТИТУЦИОННОЕ ПРАВО; АДМИНИСТРАТИВНОЕ ПРАВО; ФИНАНСОВОЕ ПРАВО / CONSTITUTIONAL LAW; ADMINISTRATIVE LAW; FINANCIAL RIGHT

Malikova Gulchexra

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Xusanov Ozod Tillabayevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Selimanova Svetlana Mixaylovna

yuridik fanlar doktori (O'zbekiston)

Xvan Leonid Borisovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Peshkova Xristina Vyacheslavovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Rossiya)

Sung Un Lee

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Janubiy Koreya)

12.00.03 - ФУҚАРОЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ТАДБИРКОРЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ОИЛА ҲУҚУҚИ. ХАЛҚАРО ХУСУСИЙ ҲУҚУҚ / ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРАВО; ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЕ ПРАВО; СЕМЕЙНОЕ ПРАВО; МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ ЧАСТНОЕ ПРАВО / CIVIL LAW; BUSINESS LAW; FAMILY LAW; PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW

Oqyulov Omonboy

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Ro'zinazarov Shuhrat Nuraliyevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Ruziyev Rustam Jabborovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Borotov Mirodiljon Xomudjonovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Toshev Boboqul Norqobilovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Shomuxamedova Zamira Shoislamovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, (O'zbekiston)

Ahmad Issa Altweissi

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Iordaniya)

12.00.04 - ФУҚАРОЛИК ПРОЦЕССУАЛ ҲУҚУҚИ. ХЎЖАЛИК ПРОЦЕССУАЛ ҲУҚУҚИ. ҲАҚАМЛИК ЖАРАЁНИ ВА МЕДИАЦИЯ / ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО; ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЕ ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО; АРБИТРАЖНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС И МЕДИАЦИЯ / CIVIL PROCEDURE LAW; ECONOMIC PROCEDURAL LAW; ARBITRATION PROCESS AND MEDIATION

Esanova Zamira Normurodovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Mamasidiqov Muzaffar Musajonovich

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Jason A.

Kanton Federal sud markazi (AQSH)

12.00.05 - МЕҲНАТ ҲУҚУҚИ. ИЖТИМОИЙ ТАЪМИНОТ ҲУҚУҚИ / ТРУДОВОЕ ПРАВО; ПРАВО СОЦИАЛЬНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ / THE LABOR LAW; SOCIAL SECURITY LAW

Usmanova Muborak Akmalxanovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Gasanov Mixail Yuriyevich

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Sattorova Gulnoza Djurakulovna

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Murodova Gulnora

yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Denisov Gleb

yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)

Fayziyev Shuxrat Xasanovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Usmonov Muhammadi Bahridinovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Xolmuminov Juma
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Jo'rayev Yuldash Achilovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Skripnikov Nikolay Kuzmich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Po'latov Baxtiyor Xalilovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Salomov Baxrom Salomovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Salayev Nodirbek Saparbayevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Osmonaliev Qayrat
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Aleksey Kibalnik
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Kudryavtsev Vladislav Leonidovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Sergey Shoshin
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Rossiya)
James B.
Eaglin Federal sud markazi (AQSH)

Rustambayev Mirzayusup Hakimovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Zufarov Rustam Axmedovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Kabulov Rustam
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Rajabova Mavjuda Abdullayevna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Taxirov Farhod
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Ismailov Isomiddin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Hamidov Nurmuhammad Orif o'g'li
yuridik fanlar bo'yicha falsafa doktori (O'zbekiston)
Yuldoshev Rifat Raxmadjonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Tojikiston)
Djansarayeva Rima Ernatovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Yelena Antonyan Aleksandrovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Matthew Light
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Kanada)

Inog'omjonova Zumratxon Fatxullayevna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Pulatov Yuriy Safiyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
To'laganova Gulchehra Zaxitovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Muxiddinov Faxriddin Muxiddinovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Mirazov Davron Miragzamovich
yuridik fanlar doktori (O'zbekiston)
Rijakov Aleksandr Petrovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)

Stoyko Nikolay Genadyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Iskandarov Zayniddin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Tojikiston)
Sergey Pen
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Aleksey Purs
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Belarus)
Jurgen Maurer
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Germaniya)
Kevin Curtin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (AQSH)

Ismoilov Bahodir Islamovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Matkarimova Gulchehra Abdusamatovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Yuldasheva Govxerjan
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Alexander Trunk
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Germaniya)

1. Бекчанов Алишер Илхамбоевич “НОРМАТИВ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ҲУЖЖАТ” ТУШУНЧАСИ: ИЛМИЙ ВА ҲУҚУҚИЙ МАЗМУНИ.....	5
2. Нариманов Бекзод Абдувалиевич НОДАВЛАТ НОТИЖОРАТ ТАШКИЛОТЛАРИ МАЪМУРИЙ ҲУҚУҚ СУБЪЕКТИ СИФАТИДА: ДАВЛАТ РЎЙХАТИДАН ЎТКАЗИШНИНГ АЙРИМ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	13
3. Алимарданова Ирода Воҳид кизи БИЗНЕС-ОМБУДСМАН: ЖАҲОН ТАЖРИБАСИ ВА УНИНГ ИСТИҚБОЛИ.....	22
4. Қазақбаев Туулбай Керимбаевич КОРПОРАТИВ ШАРТНОМА ТАРАФЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ҲУҚУҚ ВА МАЖБУРИЯТЛАРИ ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	29
5. Пўлатов Алишер Рамазанович ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА КРИПТОВАЛЮТАНИ ФУҚАРОЛИК ҲУҚУҚЛАРИ ОБЪЕКТЛАРИНИНГ ТИЗИМИДА ТУТГАН ЎРНИ.....	37
6. Саидова Нигора Акмалевна ОСОБЕННОСТИ ОНЛАЙН-УРЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ СПОРОВ В ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ.....	45
7. Fazilov Farkhod Maratovich RECEIVING GIFTS AS A MEANS OF LAUNDERING CRIMINAL PROCEEDS.....	53
8. Nosirov Barkhayot Murodjonovich CYBER SECURITY: IMPORTANCE, DEFINITION, TERMINOLOGICAL AND CONTENT DIFFERENCES.....	61
9. Тошпулатов Акром Икромович ЖИНОЯТ ҲУҚУҚИ ВАЗИФА ВА ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИНИНГ ЖИНОЯТ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ПРИНЦИПЛАР ШАКЛЛАНИШИДАГИ ЎРНИ.....	66
10. Муҳаммадиев Сарвар Асқар ўғли ЖИНОЯТ ПРОЦЕССИГА ОИД НОРМАТИВ ХУСУСИЯТГА ЭГА ҲУЖЖАТЛАРНИ ТИЗИМЛАШТИРИШДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ АХБОРОТ-ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ИМКОНИАТЛАРИНИ ҚЎЛЛАШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	77
11. Хамдамова Фируза Уразалиевна ВОПРОСЫ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ ПРАВОСУБЪЕКТНОСТИ ТРАНСНАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ КОРПОРАЦИЙ В ЦИФРОВУЮ ЭРУ И УКРЕПЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОСТИ.....	88
12. Амонов Феруз Салимович КОРРУПЦИЯГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШДА ЖАМОАТЧИЛИК НАЗОРАТИНИ АМАЛГА ОШИРИШ МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ.....	95

Nosirov Barkhayot Murodjonovich,
Independent researcher at Tashkent State University of Law
E-mail: barkhayot3389@gmail.com

CYBER SECURITY: IMPORTANCE, DEFINITION, TERMINOLOGICAL AND CONTENT DIFFERENCES

For citation: Nosirov Barkhayot Murodjonovich. CYBER SECURITY: IMPORTANCE, DEFINITION, TERMINOLOGICAL AND CONTENT DIFFERENCES. Journal of Law Research. 2023, 8 vol., issue 5, pp.61-65

<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8025308>

ANNOTATION

This article describes the basic terms and definitions of aspects of cybersecurity. Definitions are given from various sources and a thorough comparison of these definitions is carried out, including from the point of view of different authors and from the point of view of international and national legal acts. In addition, the author tried to clarify his point of view on the importance of unifying cybersecurity terminology.

Keywords: cyber security, cybercrime, information security, cyber-attacks, information, security.

Nosirov Barkhayot Murodjonovich,
Toshkent davlat yuridik universitetining mustaqil izlanuvchisi
E-mail: barkhayot3389@gmail.com

KIBER XAVFSIZLIK: MUHIMLIGI, TA'RIFI, TERMINOLOGIK VA MAZMUNY FARQLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada kiberxavfsizlikning asosiy tushunchalari va aspektlari ta'rifi berilgan. Turli manbalarda keltirilgan ta'riflar berilgan va bu ta'riflarni, jumladan, turli mualliflar nuqtai nazaridan, xalqaro va milliy huquqiy hujjatlar nuqtai nazaridan har tomonlama taqqoslash amalga oshirilgan. Bundan tashqari, muallif kiberxavfsizlik terminologiyasini unifikatsiya qilish muhimligi haqidagi o'z nuqtai nazarini atroflicha taqdim qilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kiberxavfsizlik, kiberjinoyat, axborot xavfsizligi, kiberhujumlar, axborot, xavfsizlik.

Носиров Бархаёт Муроджонович,
Самостоятельный соискатель Ташкентского
государственного юридического университета
E-mail: barkhayot3389@gmail.com

КИБЕРБЕЗОПАСНОСТЬ: ЗНАЧЕНИЕ, ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ, ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И СОДЕРЖАТЕЛЬНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье описаны основные термины и определения аспектов кибербезопасности. Приведены определения из различных источников и проведено тщательное сопоставление этих определений, в том числе с точки зрения разных авторов и с точки зрения международных и национальных правовых актов. Кроме того, автор попытался разъяснить свою точку зрения о важности унификации терминологии кибербезопасности.

Ключевые слова: кибербезопасность, киберпреступность, информационная безопасность, кибератаки, информация, безопасность.

The terminology used to discuss security aspects of digital devices and information has evolved significantly over the past two decades. While terms such as "Computer Security," "IT Security," and "Information Security" were commonly used at the beginning of the century, new terms have emerged to reflect the changing landscape of technology and security.

One of the primary drivers of this shift in terminology is the rise of the internet and the increasing connectivity of devices. As we've moved from a world of standalone computers to one in which everything from phones to cars can be connected to the internet, security concerns have become more complex and multifaceted.

One of the more recent terms to emerge in this context is "Cybersecurity," which refers to the practice of protecting internet-connected systems and networks from digital attacks. This term reflects the growing recognition that security is not just a matter of protecting individual computers or devices, but rather involves safeguarding the entire ecosystem of digital infrastructure.

This development in use of terminology is causing some issues as the term "Cyber Security" lacks the defining clarity of, for example, "Computer Security." This can lead to confusion and misunderstanding if parties have different assumptions of what the term represents. Whilst it is unlikely to be a problem in private conversations between interested citizens it becomes, at the very least, a nuisance at an organizational level and is a widely recognized issue among professionals in the field. These problems amplify if ambiguity continues in courts of justice, national cyber security strategies or international treaties. Recognizing the lack of a consistent meaning of the term cyber security as a considerable issue (Baylon, 2014; Congressional Research Service, 2014; Creasey, 2013; Internet Society, 2012). [1]

The lack of a consistent meaning of the term cyber security can be a considerable issue. The most common definition is "The act or technique of securing Internet data by protecting computer software from unauthorized access, tampering and other threats." This definition can be used in multiple ways that might not align with needs of most people.

Anatoly Alpeev PhD thinks "the concept of "security" in the modern world plays perhaps the most important role in all life processes: biological, political, economic, social, technical, territorial, etc. Therefore, it is very important not only correctly define this concept and its derivatives, but also correctly apply them for their intended purpose. Unfortunately, by now this desired result was not obtained. However, attempts to achieve it continue." [2]

According to above mentioned Anatoly Alpeev "Cyber security - security conditions from physical, spiritual, financial, political, emotional, professional, psychological, educational or other types impacts or consequences of an accident, damage, error, accident, harm or any other event in cyberspace that might be considered undesirable".[2]

Representatives of the Center for Strategic Assessments and Forecasts of the Russian Federation offer under cyber security to understand "the state of protection of national interests in the information sphere, determined by the totality of balanced interests of the individual, society and states. [4]

In exploring the definition of cybersecurity, some authors dive even further. For example, Daniel Schatz and his team analyzed the definition of cybersecurity from a government perspective. According to them "in their analysis of national cyber security strategies of European Union member

states, Falessi et al. (2012) provide terminology guidance in the annex explaining that there is no universally accepted nor straightforward definition of ‘cyber security.’ They write that some people regard cyber security as overlapping with information security but no definitive conclusion is provided. This view is shared by Wamala (2011) claiming that cyber security is a branch of information security. The paper highlights the risk of uncertain terminology and aims to provide clarification on the relative positions of cyber security and information security. It draws a link between cyber security and the global characteristic of the internet, as such distinguishing it from information security which, according to the author, rarely traverses jurisdictions. Wamala goes further in this definition claiming that cyber security focuses more on integrity and availability whereas information security is mainly concerned with confidentiality. He concludes that cyber security is information security with jurisdictional uncertainty and attribution issues. The Government of Montenegro (2013) agrees with the notion of a lack of clear definitions in this area and dedicates a full section in its cyber security strategy to this topic. Whilst the paper states that it presents definitions which are compliant with the basic meanings as understood in EU countries, it unfortunately does not actually provide a conclusion on the term cyber security but rather quotes various definitions from other sources. Baylon (2014) discusses the topic from a multinational cooperation perspective highlighting that the lack of or insufficiently agreed on definition of key terminology in the cyber and space security domains poses a major challenge to international treaties and arms control agreements. In particular, the considerably different interpretation of cyber security between western countries and both Russia and China causes complications in this context. Baylon states that the term ‘cyber security’ as such does not exist in Russian legislation or official doctrines. Instead, the concept of information security is prevalent. However, in this context, “information” represents a meaning extending outside the digital space which widens conversations into the information space in general. The author categorizes this into the Eastern approach, looking at cyber security emphasizing ‘social cohesion,’ and the Western approach, perceiving cyber security through a ‘national security prism.’ Godwin III, Kulpin, Rauscher, and Yaschenko (2014) concur with this challenge and provide bi-nationally (USA/Russia) agreed terminology for key phrases pertaining to the cyber space. Amongst these, the term ‘cyber security’ is defined as well; notably with a considerably different interpretation than found in official national cyber security strategies of most western countries. Giles and Hagestad (2013) extend on this by contrasting key terms and principles in this space as understood in each of their focus countries (USA, China, Russia). They find that there is a notably different understanding and approach between these countries. They conclude that in absence of a mutually agreed terminology, any potential for finding a real commonality of views on the nature and governance of cyberspace remains distant.” [1]

Craigen, D., Diakun-Thibault, N., Purse, R worked on the definition of cybersecurity and selected nine definitions of cybersecurity that provided the material perspectives of cybersecurity:

1. “Cybersecurity consists largely of defensive methods used to detect and thwart would-be intruders.” (Kemmerer, 2003)
2. “Cybersecurity entails the safeguarding of computer networks and the information they contain from penetration and from malicious damage or disruption.” (Lewis, 2006)
3. “Cyber Security involves reducing the risk of malicious attack to software, computers and networks. This includes tools used to detect break-ins, stop viruses, block malicious access, enforce authentication, enable encrypted communications, and on and on.” (Amoroso, 2006)
4. “Cybersecurity is the collection of tools, policies, security concepts, security safeguards, guidelines, risk management approaches, actions, training, best practices, assurance and technologies that can be used to protect the cyber environment and organization and user's assets.” (ITU, 2009)
5. “The ability to protect or defend the use of cyberspace from cyber-attacks.” (CNSS, 2010)
6. “The body of technologies, processes, practices and response and mitigation measures designed to protect networks, computers, programs and data from attack, damage or unauthorized access so as to ensure confidentiality, integrity and availability.” (Public Safety Canada, 2014)

7. “The art of ensuring the existence and continuity of the information society of a nation, guaranteeing and protecting, in Cyberspace, its information, assets and critical infrastructure.” (Canongia & Mandarino, 2014)

8. “The state of being protected against the criminal or unauthorized use of electronic data, or the measures taken to achieve this.” (Oxford University Press, 2014)

9. “The activity or process, ability or capability, or state whereby information and communications systems and the information contained therein are protected from and/or defended against damage, unauthorized use or modification, or exploitation.” (DHS, 2014) [6]

Walls et al. (2013) approach the topic from the perspective of a professional services provider (Gartner Inc.) and is thus focusing on tangible guidance for strategic decision makers. A key challenge highlighted is the ambiguity introduced by the thoughtless use of the term ‘cyber security,’ where nuanced definitions (Information Security or IT Security) are more appropriate and descriptive. They suggest that the term cyber security is only used in context of security practices related to the combination of offensive and defensive actions involving or relying upon information technology and/or operational technology environments and systems. The authors state that it marks a superset of security practices such as information security, IT security and other related practices. Stubley (2013) takes a different view to this and simplifies cyber security to information security based on a short analysis of the ‘cyber’ component which he defines to describe the use of information technology and computers. Barzilay (2013) again takes a different view and argues that cyber security must be defined through cyber risk which leads to his conclusion that cyber security is a sub-discipline of information security which is in contrast to Walls et al. (2013). In official guidance, ISACA (2014) takes yet another position stating that cyber security is emerging within the fields of information security and traditional security. Enterprises should distinguish between standard (lower-level) information security and cyber security; the difference is in the scope, motive, opportunity and method of the attack. [1]

The other very important terminology is “cybercrime”. What is cybercrime? There is no universally accepted definition of cybercrime. According to the Oxford Dictionary, cybercrime is criminal activities carried out by means of computers and the internet. The Law of Uzbekistan about cybersecurity describes cybercrimes in article 3, which states “a set of crimes committed in cyberspace using software and hardware in order to seize information, change it, destroy or hack information systems and resources” and cyber security is the state of protection of the interests of individuals, society and the state against external and internal threats in cyberspace. [5]

UNODC describes it as an act that violates the law, which is perpetrated using information and communication technology (ICT) to either target networks, systems, data, websites and/or technology and facilitate a crime (e.g., Goodman, and Brenner, 2002; Wall, 2007; Wilson, 2008; ITU, 2012; Maras, 2014; Maras, 2016). Cybercrime differs from traditional crime in that it "knows no physical or geographic boundaries" and can be conducted with less effort, greater ease, and at greater speed than traditional crime (although this depends on the type of cybercrime and type of crime it is being compared to) (Maras, 2014; for information about different types of cybercrime, see Cybercrime Module 2 on General Types of Cybercrime). [3]

Certainly, there can be a question about the importance of unification of legislatives of different countries. I would say the main one is about the efficiency of international cooperation. When two countries have a close interpretation of cybercrime issues, it is a way easier to cooperate. International cooperation can help us to fight transborder crimes and make life of criminals difficult.

Having a clear and common view on the definition of cybercrime and related terminology is a crucial first step in any international agreement on cyber security. Consistency in definitions will enable a more effective response to cyber threats, as it will ensure that all countries understand what actions are illegal and what measures are necessary to address those actions.

Standardizing definitions of cybercrime and related terminology is particularly important because cyber threats are constantly evolving, and new forms of cybercrime are emerging. By establishing a common understanding of cybercrime and related terms, countries can better collaborate on developing effective strategies to combat these new and evolving threats.

Moreover, a clear and common definition of cybercrime will help ensure that all countries are held to the same legal standards, reducing the risk of different interpretations and legal conflicts. It will also help to create a more transparent and accountable environment for cyber security.

In summary, a clear and common definition of cybercrime and related terminology is essential to enable effective international cooperation in addressing cyber threats. It is an important step towards achieving a more secure and stable cyberspace for all.

Furthermore, the evolution of security terminology reflects the ongoing evolution of technology and the growing recognition that security is a complex and multifaceted challenge that requires a range of different approaches and strategies. As new threats emerge and technology continues to evolve, it's likely that we'll continue to see new terms and concepts emerge in the world of digital security.

References/Iqtiboslar/Сноски:

1. Schatz, Daniel; Bashroush, Rabih; and Wall, Julie (2017) "Towards a More Representative Definition of Cyber Security," *Journal of Digital Forensics, Security and Law*: Vol. 12: No. 2, Article 8. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15394/jdfsl.2017.1476> Available at: <https://commons.erau.edu/jdfsl/vol12/iss2/8>
2. Алпеев, А. С. (2014). Терминология безопасности: кибербезопасность, информационная безопасность. *Вопросы кибербезопасности*, (5 (8)), 39-42. (Alpeev, A. S. (2014). Security terminology: cybersecurity, information security. *Cyber Security Issues*, (5(8)), 39-42)
3. *Cybercrime Module 1 Key Issues: Cybercrime in Brief* (unodc.org).
4. Бондаревой Алины Владимировны “Международное сотрудничество государств в сфере информационной безопасности”, *Юридический институт Кафедра конституционного и международного права*, 2018 ст 6 (Bondareva Alina Vladimirovna “International cooperation of states in the field of information security”, *Law Institute Department of Constitutional and International Law*, 2018, P. 6)
5. № 764 Law of Uzbekistan Republic about cybersecurity ЗРУ-764-сон 15.04.2022. О кибербезопасности (lex.uz)
6. Craigen, D., Diakun-Thibault, N., & Purse, R. 2014. Defining Cybersecurity. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 4(10): 13-21. <http://doi.org/10.22215/timreview/835>
7. Khamidov, N. (2022). Conditions enabling the commission of some transnational organized crimes.
8. Khamidov N. Трансмиллий жиноятлар тушунчаси ва улар учун жавобгарлик белгиланишининг ижтимоий зарурати. – 2020 (Khamidov N. The concept of transnational crimes and the social necessity of determining responsibility for them. - 2020).
9. Khamidov, Nurmukhammad. "Criminal-legal aspects of the drug abuse in some countries and imposed approaches against it." *International Journal of Legal Studies (IJOLS)* 4 (2 (2018): 177-182.
10. Salaev N., Khamidov N. Qualification Of Smuggling: Uzbek Legislation And Foreign Experience // *Ilkogretim Online*. – 2021. – Т. 20. – №. 3. – С. 1661-1667.

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

8 ЖИЛД, 5 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 8, НОМЕР 5

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 8, ISSUE 5

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000